

14 days after inoculation

28 days after inoculation

pTRV2:00
pTRV2:GbTMEM214-4
pTRV2:GbTMEM214-1
pTRV2:GbTMEM214-7

Figure S3. Comparison of phenotypes at different days after inoculation in VIGS analysis.